

A STUDY ON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFILE OF ENTERPRISES AND CHALLENGES EXPERIENCED BY ENTREPRENEURS IN AHILYANAGAR TALUKA

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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneur means an individual whose organization operates a business, enterprise or venture taking into consideration the economic and financial risks to do such activity. Entrepreneurship is basically economic / financial activity that is undertaken and carried out by one individual or group of individuals. Entrepreneurship plays significant role in economic growth and development of economy mainly through creation of utilities / services and generation of employment opportunities within short duration. This helps to transform and upgrade the standard of living and source of income of people by large. Study tried to explore the relationship between profile of enterprises and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs in Ahilyanagar taluka. Empirical study was conducted to explore the relationship between selected factors. Qualitative approach was used. Profile of enterprises was considered as independent factor and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs was considered as dependent factor. Primary data was collected from 100 individual entrepreneurs owning and managing their enterprises through conducting field survey.

Keywords: Enterprises, Challenges Experienced, Entrepreneurs, Relationship

I) INTRODUCTION

An entrepreneur means an individual whose organization operates a business, enterprise or venture taking into consideration the economic and financial risks to do such activity. He / she take number of initiatives including planning and directing the business in order to gain advantage from opportunities as decision makers decide how much, what and which goods or services will be supplied.

According to Hisrich et. al. (2017), 'An entrepreneur is defined as someone who perceives an opportunity and creates an organization to pursue it'.

According to Scarborough et. al. (2015), 'An entrepreneur means a person who habitually creates and innovates to build something of recognized value around perceived opportunities'.

Entrepreneurship is basically economic / financial activity that is undertaken and carried out by one individual or group of individuals. Entrepreneurship means making of fresh or unique combination of already prevailing materials and resources that entrepreneurship throws up as innovations, as opposed to inventions and that no one is entrepreneur forever, only when individual is actually doing the innovative activity or event. Entrepreneurship plays significant role in economic growth and development of economy mainly through creation of utilities / services and generation of employment opportunities within short duration. This helps to transform and upgrade the standard of living and source of income of people by large.

India as an emerging economy; is gifted with rich, natural, innovative and creative human resources. Country cannot lead to the path of economic growth only through technical

advancement. Such technology should be appropriately used and taken benefit by entrepreneurs. Thus, entrepreneurs are active agents and mediators of growth engine of country.

II) LITERATURE REVIEW

- Shah Heena (2013) conducted study on sixty three entrepreneurs in twelve Indian states to assess and identify the strategies and policies to create suitable environment for women in India. Case studies of successful entrepreneurs and their challenges were covered. Study examined factors acting as barriers for entrepreneurial activities. Study focused on support offered under Government schemes for starting an enterprise came essentially from informal sources.
- Bharath D. (2018) conducted research on entrepreneurial behaviour of rural women working in layer poultry farming. Women entrepreneurs mainly belonged to nuclear family and small family size. Entrepreneurs were under high level of mass media exposure.
- Ranjithkumar T. (2018) studied the attitudes and behaviours of entrepreneurs towards self-employment in Namakkal district. Study found entrepreneurs had favorable attitude towards self-employment. Entrepreneurs had medium level of information seeking behaviour. Entrepreneurs positively participated in training programs organized by department of agriculture and animal husbandry.
- Joseph Elizabeth and Vikraman Nisha (2021) investigated relation between attitude of entrepreneurs on various factors including financial management, production, human resource, marketing, problem solving and acquiring of technical knowhow for self-employment. 400 entrepreneurs were covered from Kottayam district. Study found attitude of entrepreneurs had significant impact towards self-employment of entrepreneurs.
- Arumugam U. and Manida M. (2023) conducted research on entrepreneurship in Tamil Nadu. Research studied the characteristics of a successful Agri-entrepreneur and the types of services providers. Study discussed vital role played by entrepreneurs in Indian agri-processing industry. Entrepreneurship contributed significantly (directly and indirectly) towards jobs creation in society. Study focused on areas such as need-based computing, considering socio-economic conditions, readiness, resource availability, geographic dimensions and the market for the end product.

III) RESEARCH DESIGN

1) Objective of research

- To study and explore the relationship between profile of enterprises and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs in Ahilyanagar taluka

2) Methodology

- Empirical study was conducted to explore the relationship between selected factors.
- Qualitative approach was used.
- Profile of enterprises was considered as independent factor and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs was considered as dependent factor.

3) Statement of Hypothesis

H₀: There is no relationship between profile of enterprises and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs

H₁: There is significant relationship between profile of enterprises and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs

4) Data Collection

- Primary data was collected from 100 individual entrepreneurs owning and managing their enterprises through conducting field survey.

5) Sampling Plan

- Population for study included entrepreneurs of small scale enterprises located in Ahilyanagar taluka.
- Sampling frame included entrepreneurs of retail (trading) enterprises into existence from last five years.
- Sample size was 100 individual entrepreneurs
- Sampling method was random sampling

6) Scope of study

- Study considered following five aspects regarding profile of enterprises
 - Age of enterprise
 - Nature of business
 - Ownership of enterprise
 - Location of enterprise
 - Nature of products / goods
- Study considered following ten challenges experienced by entrepreneurs
 - Unavailability of material and supplies
 - Unavailability of manpower / employees
 - Insufficient financial resources
 - Inadequate non-financial resources
 - Heavy documentation and compliances
 - Cutthroat competition and market rivalries
 - Absence of managerial skills and expertise
 - High operational expenditures
 - Difficulty in managing work life balance
 - Lack of Government support

7) Limitations of study

- Study covered only male entrepreneurs. Female (woman) entrepreneurs were not considered.

- Enterprises having annual turnover of more than Rs. 10 lakhs were not considered.
- Enterprises located outside Ahilyanagar taluka were not covered.

IV) Statistical Analysis and Inferences

Study tried to explore the relationship between profile of enterprises and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs in Ahilyanagar taluka.

Profile of enterprises which generally include demographic factors was considered as independent factor. Following five aspects were covered regarding profile of selected enterprises, i.e. age of enterprise, nature of business, ownership of enterprise, location of enterprise and nature of products / goods.

There are numerous challenges experienced by entrepreneurs in day to day running and management of enterprises that were considered as dependent factor. Study covered following ten challenges experienced by entrepreneurs i.e. unavailability of material and supplies, unavailability of manpower / employees, insufficient financial resources, inadequate non-financial resources, heavy documentation and compliances, cutthroat competition and market rivalries, absence of managerial skills and expertise, high operational expenditures, difficulty in managing work life balance and lack of government support.

Pearson Chi-Square Test for independence was used and values were calculated using SPSS Software at 95% level of confidence.

Table 1: Table showing case summary and chi-square test for relationship between profile of enterprises and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs

Cases	Case Summary					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Profile of enterprises x Challenges experienced by entrepreneurs	100	100.0%	0	0.0%	100	100.0%
Independent Variable	Profile of enterprises					
Dependent Variable	Challenges experienced by entrepreneurs					

Chi-Square Tests	Value	Degree of freedom	Significance Level (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	142.697 ^a	4	0.001
Likelihood Ratio	98.534	4	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	37.225	1	0.000
Standard Deviation	0.4759		
Mean Square	26.841		
N of Valid Cases	100		

Above table showed calculations of Pearson Chi-Square test: Chi square value = 142.697, Degree of freedom = 4, Mean Square = 26.841, $p > 0.05$.

Result: By applying the chi-square test, it was inferred that there existed significant relationship / association between both the factors under study. Therefore, the null hypothesis stood rejected and alternate hypothesis got accepted.

V) CONCLUSION

Study concluded that there existed significant relationship / association between the profile of enterprises and challenges experienced by the entrepreneurs in Ahilyanagar taluka.

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